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Deliverable D4.2 - Optimization approaches for improving energy efficiency and durability

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Optimization approaches for improving energy efficiency and durability

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Table of contents

1 INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 Steel ladle refining	1
1.2 Continuous casting.....	3
2 REDUCTION OF GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS THROUGH THE ACCURATE PREDICTION OF THE STEEL LADLE TEMPERATURE.....	4
2.1 Problem description.....	4
2.2 Modelling approaches	5
2.3 Enhancing the thermal management of the ladle	7
2.4 Results and discussions.....	8
2.5 Future work.....	10
3 REDUCE EMISSIONS THROUGH IMPROVED LADLE LOGISTICS.....	10
3.1 Problem statement	10
3.2 Optimization approaches.....	11
3.3 Results and discussion	12
4 IMPROVING THE LIFETIME OF REFRACTORIES IN CONTINUOUS CASTING	16
4.1 Problem statement	16
4.2 Modelling approaches	17
4.3 Data-driven approaches.....	18
4.4 Clogging detection and prediction in Continuous Casting.....	18
5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS	20
6 REFERENCES.....	20

1 Introduction

Steel, cement, glass, and superalloys are essential materials in our society. Steel is the most reliable material for engineering, construction, automobiles, white goods, and industrial equipment. With a global steel production of 1.8 billion tons annually and an expected growth rate of 1-1.4 % per year, the global steel demand will be around 1.9 billion tons by 2035 [1]. The Iron & Steel (I&S) industry is the largest end-user of refractory products, accounting for 68 % of the international market. The competition in and out of the European territory is very intense. Due to rising production costs and the European Green Deal, the urgent challenge for the industry is to stay competitive and invest in breakthrough technologies for decarbonization.

Much is still unknown about how the new breakthrough technologies will affect refractory consumption. Hence, maximizing energy efficiency and durability of the refractories within the existing processes is a key lever to improve the sustainability of the I&S industry. Advanced digital methods can be leveraged to enhance the energy efficiency and durability of refractories in steelmaking. This involves developing real-time monitoring systems and machine learning techniques to collect and analyse data on steel ladles and continuous casting systems. Insights from this data, combined with detailed simulations and optimization techniques, can be used to optimize decision-making and achieve more sustainable operations. This report will describe the main methods available in the literature and discuss different approaches to improve the sustainability of both the steel ladle operations and the continuous casting process. In each case, the problem will be described, the available approaches discussed and some initial results presented.

To withstand the high temperatures involved in the iron and steel making processes, refractory materials need to be used. They are employed in internal linings of furnaces, metal and slag transportation vessels and continuous casting equipment, for example. A comprehensive list of the most common materials used in the different iron and steel making processes is presented in [2]. In the context of Task 4.2, two essential applications of the refractories are investigated in detail: steel ladle refining and continuous casting.

1.1 Steel ladle refining

Steel ladles play an essential role in the logistics of a steel plant, being responsible for moving molten steel from tapping at primary refining, undergoing secondary metallurgy treatments, and finally reaching the casting machines for producing the steel slabs. After casting, the ladles undergo several treatment processes until they are ready again to receive the molten steel. This is the so-called ladle cycle, which is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - The steel ladle cycle. E represents the energy consumption and T the refractory temperature.

Steel ladles are usually constructed with multiple layers of refractory linings: working layer, the permanent layers (safety and insulating layers) and the shell, depicted in Figure 2. The refractory linings help to reduce steel temperature losses and protect the steel shell from melting due to the high temperatures in the process. Additionally, the ladle can be divided into three sections: slag line, wall, and bottom. These layers and sections are constructed from different refractory materials selected for their specific properties and applications. A proper design ensures efficient and safe steel production, highlighting the importance of maintaining high-quality refractory linings in steel ladles.

Figure 2 - Steel ladle refractory lining [3].

Proper management of the ladle availability and logistics is then a critical aspect of the steelmaking process [4]. Ladle dispatching decisions involve defining the timing of the empty ladle operations and assigning a proper ladle to all charges for a given production schedule. The cycle begins when a ladle is assigned to a charge of molten steel. After casting, the remaining slag must be poured before it can be transported to undergo empty ladle operations. Three different operations are commonly applied when a ladle is empty [5]:

- **Maintenance:** The ladle needs to be repaired, during the cycle, in a tilting stand. It involves changing sliding plates, removing solidified slag, and adding filler sand, for example. In addition, the refractory lining can be inspected by taking measurements of its thickness and temperature.

- **Heating:** Ladle stands are equipped with burners that can be optionally used to re-heat the ladles during the cycle. This operation is required to adjust the refractory temperature before tapping.
- **Waiting:** The ladle can wait before and after transportation to the primary refining installations. After that, it is ready to receive the molten steel from the next assigned charge.

Temperature losses and excessive refractory wear can be avoided by better controlling the ladle's thermal state during its operations, which can be translated into lower emissions and energy savings for steelmakers [6]. This includes defining the sequence of charges assigned to each ladle and for how long it should wait and be heated during each cycle. Therefore, considering the thermal behaviour of the ladle becomes an essential aspect of optimized ladle logistics.

1.2 Continuous casting

Continuous casting (CC) is a crucial process in steelmaking, enabling the efficient production of high-quality steel products by continuously solidifying molten steel into long, uninterrupted lengths. The key elements of this process are displayed in Figure 3. The process begins with molten steel flowing from the ladle into the tundish, which serves as a reservoir and refining step. In addition, it provides a controlled and steady flow of molten steel into the mold. Various control devices are used to regulate this flow and ensure uniform distribution of steel, which is essential to have defect-free products.

Figure 3 - The continuous casting process layout [7].

The initial steel solidification occurs at the mold, forming a solid outer shell around the molten steel as it descends through the casting machine. As the semi-solidified steel leaves from the mold, it enters the secondary cooling zones, where thermal management becomes critical. The cooling rate must be carefully controlled to ensure even solidification throughout the steel's cross-section, minimizing surface and internal defects. Effective thermal control in these zones is essential to ensure the final product's structural integrity and surface quality. By streamlining the conversion of molten steel into semi-finished forms such as slabs, billets, or blooms, continuous casting has transformed modern steel production. This process not only enhances production efficiency but also improves product consistency, reduces material waste and lowers operational costs compared to traditional casting methods.

2 Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions through the accurate prediction of the steel ladle temperature

2.1 Problem description

In the steelmaking industry, maintaining the correct temperature at the continuous casting is critical for process stability. Too high temperatures can cause steel to become overly fluid, leading to breakouts in the mold. Conversely, if the temperature is too low, it can lead to premature solidification, resulting in nozzle clogging [8]. A significant factor in temperature drops during secondary steelmaking is the thermal loss from steel ladles, which is often poorly understood due to inadequate descriptions of their thermal status. Steel shops typically use "safety" margins by targeting higher temperatures than necessary. This is because reheating steel needs significantly more energy and time than cooling it down. By starting with a higher temperature, steel shops ensure that the steel does not fall below the proper temperature range for following processes [9]. This approach results in additional energy consumption and unnecessary CO₂ emissions from hot metal, electricity, or natural gas [10]. Therefore, it is essential to develop methods for accurately predicting the thermal status of steel ladles throughout their lifecycle. Improved predictions would reduce the need for large safety margins and, ultimately, decrease CO₂ emissions, which is the primary goal of this research.

Steel ladles are used to transport steel from Basic Oxygen Furnace (BOF) or Electrical Arc Furnace (EAF) tapping to the continuous caster, as well as to perform secondary metallurgy operations. During this transportation process, ladles play an important role in maintaining the molten steel's temperature. The above-mentioned operations, which occur in the ladle, include refining the steel composition, removing impurities, and adjusting the temperature of the steel to guarantee optimal casting conditions.

Controlling the steel temperature at Continuous Casting (CC) arrival is crucial. Tracking the ladle's thermal state throughout its cycle plays a key role, but there is no clear definition of the ladle's thermal state in the literature. Figure 1 illustrates the steel ladle's cycle and highlights the importance of monitoring its thermal state. After completing continuous casting, each ladle proceeds to a maintenance station. Additionally, the ladle can wait empty before tapping the steel. During this idle period, the ladle loses significant energy, leading to a decrease in the refractory temperature. The ladle is placed under a burner for reheating before tapping to counteract this. However, based on discussions with steelmaking experts, reheating is usually not based on the ladle's current thermal state in the steel plants, resulting in substantial energy loss during this phase.

To address this issue of energy loss during ladle cycle, this report proposes basing the reheating process on the ladle's current thermal state, potentially leading to significant energy savings. To have an accurate representation of the total energy content, which is required for the online prediction model, the steel ladle would need to be continuously monitored throughout its lifetime. It is possible to do this for one cycle using thermocouples, however, over the lifetime of the ladle it is impractical to carry out direct physical measurements of the ladle's temperature and as such various numerical models and data driven techniques will now be discussed. These techniques, including thermal simulations and machine learning models, will be used to estimate the ladle's thermal state in real-time, providing a more accurate solution for reheating and minimizing energy losses.

2.2 Modelling approaches

The literature on the steel-making process encompasses various studies aiming to predict the temperature of steel, tracking the thermal profile of refractory linings in steel ladles and investigating their influence on steel temperature within secondary metallurgy. Accurate temperature control is critical for maintaining steel quality and optimizing energy efficiency. The approaches employed to achieve these goals are categorized into two main types: numerical models and data-driven models.

2.2.1 Numerical Models

This section reviews key numerical models that predict ladle temperature, including methods like the Finite Element Method and computational fluid dynamics. These models provide insights into heat loss, refractory thermal status and real-time temperature monitoring, all aimed at optimizing the thermal management in the steelmaking process.

A two-dimensional mathematical model has been developed by [11] to analyse the temperature dynamics of steel ladles during continuous casting. This model, validated against real thermocouple data, integrates energy balance and refractory thermal profiles. It assumes a homogenous molten steel with minimal effect on temperature gradients and has been implemented in MATLAB using the Finite Element Method (FEM). The model accounts for conduction and radiation heat losses and allows user-friendly input of ladle parameters, including geometry and thermal properties of refractory layers. While focusing on working lining temperatures and excluding the shell, the model has effectively predicted temperature trends compared to previous linings.

An online system for real-time monitoring and prediction of liquid steel temperature in ladles and tundish has been explored by [12]. This system combines analytical and statistical methods to calculate temperature profiles and heat balances, considering refractory properties and preheating factors. Continuous temperature prediction throughout steel processing has enhanced operational efficiency and product quality, enabling accurate control over ladle temperature, optimizing casting conditions, and minimizing risks associated with thermally unsuitable ladles. However, the lack of detailed references for the system's models raises questions about validity and transparency.

The critical role of temperature control in steelmaking for maintaining steel quality has been highlighted by [13]. A one-dimensional mathematical model has been introduced to predict ladle temperature, aiding real-time monitoring. The model's computational efficiency facilitates integration into steel production control systems for continuous monitoring. Although limited in accurately modelling tapping and casting, the model prevents error accumulation over time. Challenges include obtaining realistic parameters for ladle materials, which require future experimental validation. Overall, the model presents promising prospects for enhancing steel production efficiency and quality through improved temperature control.

A finite difference model has been applied by [14] to predict the thermal state of the ladle. This one-dimensional model focuses on heat losses between walls and steel baths for online monitoring of the ladle's thermal behaviour. Validated using data from [15], the model performs well for the full ladle but fails to predict the temperature of the innermost and outer shell refractories during the cooling process.

The understanding of ladle heat preservation has been enhanced by [16] through the application of the Finite Volume Method (FVM) for 3D modelling of combustion and fluid-solid heat transfer during

online preheating and the use of ladle lids. Numerical analysis using Fluent software and the Weighted Sum of Grey Gases Model (WSGGM) for flue gases' variable emissivity and absorptivity has demonstrated that the ladle lid effectively reduces temperature drops. Online preheating for 10-30 minutes significantly raises the working lining's temperature, with effects comparable to full operation with the lid after 30 minutes. These findings highlight the benefits of optimized heat preservation strategies in steelmaking.

A comprehensive transient numerical analysis of steel ladle refractory linings, considering temperature-dependent properties, has been conducted by [3] to optimize energy efficiency and cost. Using FEM via Abaqus software, the study achieves a detailed understanding of energy consumption and thermal dynamics during ladle cycles. The proposed method simulates various lining configurations, providing insights into energy efficiency and cost-effectiveness. Challenges include the accuracy of high operational temperatures on inner linings and potential time-dependent deformation in specific configurations.

A method combining a one-dimensional heat transfer model and regression analysis has been presented by [17] to regulate casting superheat temperature. This model employs the finite difference method to predict steel temperature by focusing on the relationship between tapping and casting temperatures and emphasizes the importance of the ladle's thermal state during transportation. The model calculates the initial refractory lining status based on the ladle's lifespan and has been validated using real data from a radiation pyrometer. While addressing complex processes like holding and teeming with an analytical model, the study indicates potential areas for refinement due to the use of one-dimensional heat equations.

The crucial role of thermal stratification in liquid steel within ladles, impacting superheat availability at continuous casters and subsequent casting parameters, has been studied by [18]. A surrogate model, developed using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations and regression techniques, successfully predicts temperature profiles with over 96 % accuracy within a ± 5 K range. This model bridges the gap between fast, simplified methods and slower CFD simulations, offering online predictions vital for real-time control systems. The study opens possibilities for further applications in steelmaking processes such as ladle teeming and continuous casting.

2.2.2 Data-driven Models

Based on the review in section 2.2.1, the papers explore the physical and, particularly, CFD models for temperature prediction. The 1D models can be used for fast and roughly online prediction, sometimes reducing accuracy [19]. On the other hand, by increasing the dimension of the model, the accuracy increases, but for further application, the dimension of data would be higher which might increase the computational time and cost. Other studies apply data-driven and machine-learning algorithms to reduce computational time and cost in this problem while maintaining accuracy.

A hybrid model integrating ladle thermal status and artificial neural networks has been presented in [20] to predict molten steel temperature, addressing inaccuracies in single-model predictions and the neglect of ladle thermal conditions. They have developed forward and backward prediction models for steelmaking plants, ensuring precise temperature control. Ladle thermal tracking has been divided into phases, incorporating influential factors. The ladle lining temperature has been measured using thermocouples, and ladle thermal status has been defined using factors like cooling and preheating time. Actual ladle conditions have been encoded to aid in thermal state evaluation. The model compensates for total temperature loss and employs ANN algorithms for steel temperature prediction,

although requiring extensive input variables. Despite the constraints of the encoding method, the study offers valuable insights into ladle thermal state evaluation and temperature prediction.

A hybrid model combining a convolutional neural network (CNN), and deep neural network (DNN) has been explored by [21] to predict temperature zones in the continuous casting process of steelmaking. They have shown that by integrating temperature data from a finite differential method (FDM) into CNN and process parameters into DNN, the model achieves 97% accuracy, outperforming traditional methods. Faster computation times have been demonstrated, suggesting practical applicability in real-world steelmaking. Data generation has involved filling feature ranges for DNN training, while a software tool has converted temperature distribution into images compatible with CNN. This approach promises reduced control time without requiring additional PID controllers, highlighting its potential for industrial implementation.

An improved backpropagation (BP) neural network has been developed by [22], analysing extensive production data to predict steel temperature during production. They have optimized the model using a momentum gradient descent method, enhancing prediction accuracy. Its application in steel production processes, including BOF/EAF steelmaking, Ladle Furnace (LF) refining, and RH refining vacuum degasser, has enabled real-time temperature monitoring and management. Predictions have facilitated proactive adjustments to parameters influencing steel temperatures, such as energy usage and chemical reactions, leading to improved product quality and reduced energy consumption. Future work has been suggested to focus on refining the model to consider diverse production conditions and collect more comprehensive data for enhanced prediction accuracy.

Predictive models for estimating the cooling rate of liquid steel in ladles during continuous casting have been introduced by [23], addressing the need for quality and energy efficiency in steel production. They have used FEM simulations and machine learning techniques like decision trees, linear regression, and neural networks to enable real-time prediction of cooling rates, overcoming the limitations of traditional numerical models. Despite challenges such as the black-box nature of neural networks and the limited precision of decision trees, combining these methods has enhanced predictive accuracy. Implemented in the monitoring system of an electric steel plant, these models have facilitated precise temperature control throughout the steel production process. However, the lack of comprehensive evaluation due to limited long-term operational data remains a noted weakness, which could provide a more robust assessment of the predictive modules' effectiveness.

2.3 Enhancing the thermal management of the ladle

Based on the previous literature review, which highlighted various methods for predicting steel temperature and tracking the thermal profile of refractory linings in steel ladles, this study introduces a novel approach to enhance the thermal state tracking of steel ladles. The literature revealed that while numerous models exist, there is no exact and quantitative way to define the thermal state of a ladle, nor is it efficient to track the thermal state of all ladle layers. To address these gaps, this section will:

- define the reduced thermal state of the ladle and develop a method to identify it,
- investigate the requirements for the ladle's heating, and,
- develop a digital tool for tracking ladle temperature in steelmaking plants.

To achieve these objectives, a thermal model from ArcelorMittal was employed, linked to Python for ease of use and analyse. This model, using Finite Volume Method to simulate ladle temperatures over time for different surfaces, resulted in a high-dimensional dataset. A reduced-order model, Proper

Orthogonal Decomposition (POD), were utilized to simplify the data, focusing on significant modes that impact the thermal state. POD is a mathematical model that effectively reduces computational complexity in numerical simulations. Additionally, a machine learning algorithm called Autoencoder (AE) was used to improve dimensionality reduction and accuracy. AE is an unsupervised artificial neural network that compresses and encodes the original data efficiently, then reconstructs the data from the reduced encoded representation. AE reduces data dimensions by learning to ignore noise.

2.4 Results and discussions

A thermal model was applied to predict the temperatures of 108 different surfaces of a steel ladle including wall, bottom, and the cover, throughout the entire secondary metallurgy cycle for 20 unique steelmaking scenarios. Each scenario started at room temperature and included a preheating phase for 12 hours. The model generated a high-dimensional dataset representing the temperature profiles over time for all the combined scenarios. After simulating the required data, dimensionality reduction was performed at four different reduction levels (3, 5, 7 and 9) for both POD and AE.

First, POD was used to evaluate how each temperature mode contributes to reconstructing the original data. Each mode characterizes a distinct pattern in the temperature profiles, capturing different levels of variability within the dataset. Higher modes capture more slight variations, while the lower modes keep the dominant thermal behaviour. The analysis showed that reducing the original data to 7 modes was sufficient to maintain most of the important information. These 7 modes captured the most significant temperature variations in the ladle, ensuring that the reconstructed data matched the original temperatures. Beyond the 7th mode, the further modes contributed minimally to the accuracy of the reconstruction, as they primarily captured noise or minor fluctuations in the data.

Next, a Single-layer Autoencoder (SAE) was initially applied, which consists of a simple encoder and decoder architecture without hidden layers. It was effective but limited in its ability to keep complex patterns in the data. After several experiments, Deep Autoencoder (DAE) was identified as a more powerful algorithm compared to SAE. The DAE employs multiple layers in both the encoder and decoder, improving efficiency and accuracy. By performing a grid search, various DAE configurations were tested by changing the number of layers and neurons. Before applying the AE models, it was necessary to normalize the dataset using the min-max scaling technique. The results are summarized in Table 1, where it is possible to see that AE models constantly outperformed POD in reconstructing temperature profiles, achieving lower Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) values across all reduction levels.

Table 1: Comparison between POD and AE by using Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE)

Method	Reduction level Encoder hidden layer	Dimension 3		Dimension 5		Dimension 7		Dimension 9	
		RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE
DAE 1	[150, 70, 25]	5.72	2.35	4.51	1.96	3.34	1.52	3.36	1.48
DAE 2	[200, 100, 50, 20]	4.46	2.14	3.68	1.5	3.82	1.63	3.84	1.71
DAE 3	[200, 150, 80, 40, 20]	9.09	5.38	3.49	1.43	4.82	2.95	4.6	1.7
DAE 4	[90, 80, 60, 40, 20]	6.7	2.59	5.2	2.51	5.59	2.68	3.57	1.46
SAE	-	19.09	8.31	15.78	7.17	13.8	6.57	9	3.45
POD	-	38.18	21.49	18.61	11.47	10.19	5.6	5.75	2.67

To illustrate the results after reconstruction, a specific steelmaking scenario was chosen to test the dimensionality reduction methods. Figure 4 shows the reconstruction results for the selected

scenario using both POD and DAE methods. These figures demonstrate how well each method can reconstruct temperature from reduced-dimensional data. The quality of the reconstruction depends on the level of reduction and the specific configuration of the AE model. The charts on the left compare the original and reconstructed temperature data across different layers of the ladle, namely the wall, bottom and cover, using POD. Similarly, the charts on the right show the reconstruction error for the AE method, focusing on the wall, bottom, and cover of the ladle. In all the charts, the top line pictures the layer closest to the molten steel, known as the working layer, while the bottom line represents the metallic shell of the ladle.

Figure 4 - Comparison between the original and reconstructed data using two methods: left) POD and right) AE. Solid lines represent the original data, while the reconstructed data is in dashed lines.

The previous results for the AE model were obtained using a learning rate of 0.001, which was carefully selected to ensure stable training and optimal performance. The learning rate is a crucial parameter in machine learning algorithms, as it influences both the speed of convergence and the final accuracy of the model. A well-chosen learning rate prevents the model from either converging too slowly or overshooting optimal solutions. Figure 5 explains the learning curves for the best AE architecture used, demonstrating how the optimized learning rate contributed to the model's stable training and high performance.

Figure 5 - Learning curve of the deep Autoencoder.

The AE models consistently produced lower reconstruction errors, even for high reduction levels, which is indicating a superior capacity for dimensionality reduction while maintain data integrity. However, it should be noted that POD was faster to apply, making it a more efficient choice when computational speed is a key factor. Despite this, the improved accuracy of AE algorithms across various reduction levels highlights their effectiveness in keeping the essential patterns of the thermal data, making them a more reliable option for applications in thermal state tracking of steel ladles.

2.5 Future work

As was mentioned previously, the steel temperature in continuous casting (CC) is crucial in secondary metallurgy. Accurate estimation of the ladle's thermal state is essential for deciding on reheating after waiting times, reducing energy losses, and ensuring appropriate casting temperatures (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - The temperature of steel and ladle from end of CC of cycle n-1 to the end of CC cycle n.

For this objective, a reinforcement-learning model will be developed to estimate reheating time based on the predicted thermal state. This model considers various operational scenarios and phases within a ladle's cycle, including maintenance, tapping, and waiting times, to predict the lowest acceptable temperature for starting CC and optimize reheating strategies. The reinforcement learning approach will allow for continuous adaptation and improvement of reheating predictions, enhancing operational efficiency and energy savings in the steelmaking process.

3 Reduce emissions through improved ladle logistics

3.1 Problem statement

Mathematical programming techniques are used to determine the decision variables (solution) that optimize (minimize or maximize) an objective function subject to a set of constraints. Steel ladle

logistics can be modelled as a scheduling optimization problem using Mixed-Integer linear Programming (MILP) techniques. It entails representing the relevant decisions involved (Figure 1) through analytical equations, leveraging state-of-the-art algorithms for its efficient solution. The most common approaches to solving MILP problems can be classified as:

- Exact algorithms: these include branch and bound variants and decomposition approaches
- Heuristics: these methods are used to find a feasible solution in a short time. It entails the use of greedy, local, and global search approaches.
- Meta-heuristics: usually capable of obtaining good solutions, although they cannot guarantee optimality. Evolutionary computing techniques are often employed for this task.

Exact methods have the advantage of reaching optimality or at least providing solution guarantees, i.e., they can quantify how far a solution is from the global optimum. Therefore, they are selected to tackle the problem of understanding the most energy-efficient ladle deployment decisions. They are a promising tool to understand how to improve the energy efficiency and sustainability of steel ladle operations.

This section starts by presenting the main approaches available in the literature in the context of steel ladle logistics optimization. Next, it is discussed how to incorporate the ladle's thermal balance into a scheduling optimization model and efficiently solve it with exact MILP algorithms. Finally, the current results are presented, and the contributions to improving the steelmaking process' sustainability are highlighted.

3.2 Optimization approaches

The consideration of green objectives, such as reducing the carbon footprint and energy consumption, has recently become popular among industrial optimization applications [24]. A relevant problem in the literature is the so-called steelmaking-continuous-casting (SCC) scheduling [25], [26]. It can determine in what sequence, at what time, and on which device molten steel should be arranged at the various production stages involved [27]. The usual formulation and solution of this problem are done within an offline, or static, schedule for a given time horizon. It is often classified as a flexible job-shop scheduling problem with strict time continuity constraints in the last stage, which is known to be extremely challenging to solve as the problem size increases. Hence, developing methods to solve realistic instances has received considerable attention in the literature [28].

A systematic review of the SCC scheduling literature has been presented in [25]. The author emphasizes that most of the literature analysed has limited applicability due to several simplifications applied to the problem. This includes premises that assume no transportation limitations between processes, constant timing of the operations, workforce restrictions, no unexpected events and maintenance. It is also mentioned that the available methods are different mainly in the mathematical approach to their solution. An important insight discussed by the author is the necessity of having human supervision, especially to keep the scheduling model up-to-date and handle unexpected process disturbances.

It is clear from Section 1.1 that ladles are an essential part of the scheduling problem, as one must use them to transport the molten steel until it reaches the casting machines. However, the literature often overlooks its critical role in a steel plant [25]. Hence, the role of ladles during SCC scheduling is not well discussed in the optimization literature. The available methods differ mainly concerning the mathematical approach to their solution and which ladle dispatching constraints are considered in the model. They are discussed in more details in the next paragraphs. The ladle dispatching problem formulated as a variation of the Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) with soft time windows has been proposed by [29]. This means that a ladle picks up and delivers one heat at a time, but the full-ladle

processing time can vary and the time to service the caster can be adjusted, but not violate the overall completion time.

An integrated production scheduling system composed of four modules: database, user interface, simulation, and optimization is discussed in [30]. A MILP formulation is proposed aiming to minimize the amount of time to process all tasks (makespan), but also considering plant buffers and the assignment of steel ladles to each charge. The authors split each major decision within sub-modules, adding at the end a set of equations that connect all of them. In the ladle scheduling sub-module, a fixed number of ladles is specified alongside constraints related to the ladle's level of impurity and chemical element to be controlled. A remarkable contribution made by the authors was to consider decisions regarding the setup of casting/ingot machines, which are not commonly found in the literature.

An energy-efficient SCC formulation with integrated production and ladle scheduling problems has been presented in [31]. It considers a more comprehensive set of constraints, such as ladle preparation steps after casting (sanding, sliding plate, and water gap change). According to the author, energy efficiency is achieved by including the minimization of: (i) waiting time between adjacent operations to reduce temperature drops; (ii) idle time between two successive jobs; and (iii) completion time. A heuristic method that combines a scatter search algorithm with a MILP solver was developed to solve this problem. Moreover, a formulation that explicitly includes a model to estimate steel temperature drops due to waiting times and penalties for charges reaching the caster below superheat temperature has been discussed by [32]. The authors use a linear model estimated from historical data for simplification of the problem. A multi-objective hybrid genetic algorithm combined with local search was developed to tackle this problem. This work is an excellent example that can be further improved by including more details about the ladle logistics and refractory lifetime.

In [33] the authors discuss an integrated planning and scheduling problem formulation that extends the work from [30]. It includes a complete set of operational considerations and information about the previous schedule as inputs. Moreover, ladles are considered in the optimization problem. Constraints are included to ensure that for a given solution they (i) do not arrive too late for the next charge, (ii) do not wait more than the maximum allowed time and (iii) dirty ladles are not assigned to charges that require a clean one. An interesting approach presented is to define hard and soft constraints and then apply different penalties for their violation instead of returning unfeasible solutions. To tackle this problem, a meta-heuristic approach was developed based on the Simulated Annealing algorithm.

The ladle scheduling problem in the empty-ladle stage operations has been studied in [34]. The authors assume that a production schedule is given and tries to optimize the allocation of ladles for that scenario using meta-heuristics. This is an interesting approach and different than what has been previously proposed in the literature. Based on this idea, a more complete formulation that considers the availability of tilting and heating stands, and explicitly includes the thermal balance of the refractory lining, was proposed by [6]. Using MILP solvers and piecewise-linear models for solving this complex optimization problem, the authors provide a complete discussion on the energy efficiency of the deployment decisions.

3.3 Results and discussion

A MILP model that incorporates the thermal balance of the steel ladles was proposed as part of this task. The complete description is already published and can be found in [6]. The proposed model is a hard-to-solve combinatorial optimization problem. Its objective is to minimize the sum of heating and waiting times for the empty ladle stages (Figure 1). Extra complexity is introduced by applying the

energy balance constraints. Using piecewise linear models with logarithmic coding to approximate the nonlinearities arising from the thermal balance makes its solution possible with exact algorithms. This approach is selected to leverage the capabilities of state-of-the-art MILP solvers, which can reach optimality or at least provide solution guarantees. The optimization problem was implemented in Python 3.10 with the Pyomo 6.5 modelling language. Gurobi was selected as the optimization solver.

A pre-requisite is having an accurate predictive model for the thermal state of the steel ladle. Since piecewise-linear models are employed, the solution method is generic and not tailored for a specific use-case. Therefore, if the input/output requirements defined in [6] are met, it is easy to extend it to different use cases. For Tata Steel, IJmuiden, a reduced-order model (ROM) developed by the Ceramics Research Centre is currently available and has been successfully used. The thermal state of the ladle is represented by the average refractory temperature. An example of the model outputs is displayed in Figure 7. Different definitions have not been explored yet but using an explicit energy process indicator is a promising direction.

Figure 7 - Thermal state of the ladle during one cycle [6].

Next, production data should be used to generate instances of the optimization problem. The following information is required for each steel charge: steel tapping start time, casting start time and casting duration. Finally, the remaining parameters should be also estimated from historical data, especially the transportation and maintenance times. Ensuring that this data is accurate is essential to enable the generation of representative instances. In addition, ensuring that the dynamics of the production are respected should also be considered. For example, charges are produced in a sequence, called a cast. Since the production is continuous, it may not be always realistic to generate instances with incomplete casts.

As an example, Figure 8 shows the optimal ladle deployment decisions for a real schedule generated from production data. Note that all charges are assigned to a ladle, and the order of the empty-ladle stages is respected. This result also illustrates that the ladles should not wait for too long after heating and before tapping the next steel charge. Letting a ladle cool down after re-heating is undesired since the temperature losses are more intense at higher temperatures. This operational practice can be employed by steelmakers to improve energy efficiency and increase the refractory lifetime because of reduction in the temperature variation.

Figure 8 - Example of optimal ladle schedule. The ladle schedule is displayed in the top Gantt chart (Ladle 1-5) and machine schedule in the bottom Gantt chart. MT, HT and WT represent the maintenance, heating and waiting for tap stages, respectively (Figure 1).

The refractory thermal profiles for different lifetimes are displayed in Figure 9. It can be noted that slightly different deployment decisions are obtained depending on the condition of the ladle. Increasing the lifetime reduces the refractory thickness and results in a different thermal behaviour. For example, note that heating time required for the last charge of Ladle 1 reduces as we increase the refractory lifetime. However, the temperature decrease is much more pronounced before heating. Moreover, at least two ladles were required to be cooled down significantly. This results from short casting sequences with a significant break between them. Furthermore, the heating is more efficient when the refractory is at a lower temperature. This shows how important it is to consider the thermal balance of the ladles to dispatch steel ladles. It enabled the exact amount of idle and heating times to be computed to maximize the energy efficiency of the process.

Figure 9 - Optimal thermal profile for different ladle lifetimes.

Expanding on the previous example, the systematic application of the optimization model enabled the validation/legitimization of the following operation rules required for energy-efficient ladle logistics [6]:

1. Ladles should only be re-heated close to tapping;
2. Avoid ladles at elevated temperatures;
3. A strict temperature requirement demands more ladles in circulation;

Moreover, the optimization model also showed that improved thermal management of the steel ladles leads to a reduction in process variability. In addition, steel temperature losses can be reduced by approximately 3 °C depending on the refractory temperature requirement (Figure 10). It can result in further savings in emissions during primary and secondary metallurgy. This result highlights the trade-off between emissions from heating the ladles and steel temperature losses.

Figure 10 - The compromise between the emissions and steel temperature losses. The bars display the average CO₂ emissions per charge and the line the average steel temperature losses [6].

The previous results show the potential of the proposed model in understanding the energy-efficiency of empty-ladle operations. However, more work is required to reduce the solution time and enable the solution of more complex production scenarios, which is required for its application in a real-time setting. Preliminary results show that using optimal piecewise-linear fitting algorithms to reduce the number of linear pieces can reduce the computational effort and increase the approximation quality [35]. In addition, exploring the problem structure can also be leveraged to design strengthening cuts and reduce the solution space.

While there is work ongoing in this area [6], there is potential to expand it. In particular, incorporating sustainability indicators into the optimization objectives and the effect of the refractory lining thickness in the temperature predictions. Pre-heating ladles and then heating them during the cycle is currently a large source of direct CO₂ emissions as the existing equipment usually relies on natural gas burners [10]. Hence, employing optimization methods will be important to reduce energy losses and maximize the efficiency of heating applied until the technology leveraging clean fuels is not readily available.

4 Improving the lifetime of refractories in continuous casting

4.1 Problem statement

In the objective to leverage digital technologies for the optimization of the refractory lifetime in the continuous casting process, a first step is the development of new numerical tools that can support live decision making. The basis for such new tools should be founded on a pertinent combination of sensors that can provide input for numerical models able to anticipate future evolutions of the key parameters in the continuous casting process.

The most significant challenge in the continuous casting (CC) process is the clogging which can occur in the Submerged Entry Nozzle (SEN) as well as near the stopper region in the tundish (see Figure 3). Clogging occurs when solid inclusions, such as oxides and precipitates, accumulate on the inner walls of the SEN or near the stopper, obstructing the flow of molten steel. This obstruction can lead to flow instability, causing casting defects such as surface cracks, internal inclusions and segregation. Additionally, frequent clogging events disrupt production, resulting in increased downtime and higher operational costs.

Clogging is linked to the interaction between molten steel and non-metallic inclusions, variations in temperature and chemical reactions with refractory materials [36]. Due to the increase in the demands for varying grades of steel, the complexity of cast products has increased. Despite advancements in CC technology, SEN clogging remains a persistent problem, particularly for high-alloy or deoxidized steels. Addressing this issue is vital for enhancing the reliability and efficiency of the continuous casting process, reducing the frequency of blockages and minimizing casting defects.

Ensuring uniformity and high-quality output in CC requires advanced monitoring and control systems. The continuous casting process generates vast amounts of data from sensors that monitor temperature, flow rates and other critical parameters. By leveraging the real-time recorded data, the modern tools like artificial intelligence can be leveraged to optimise and make decisions based on these data to take preventive measures to reduce the operational inefficiencies in CC.

Figure 11 illustrates the flow of molten steel from the tundish to the mold through the flow control devices. The SEN and the stopper regulate the flow of molten steel, which is essential for maintaining the casting sequence. A build-up of solid or semi-solid material often forms on the surface of the refractory materials used in flow control devices, which can pose significant challenges during the steel casting sequence. These formations of non-metallic inclusions interact with the refractory and can lead to clogging.

Figure 11 - Illustration of the clogging phenomena in Submerged Entry Nozzle (SEN) during CC.

As part of Task 4.2, a deep learning-based approach will be employed in stages to predict clogging. In the starting phase, the deep learning model will aim to predict key process parameters based on historical data, the following phase will then aim to predict clogging. The expected outcomes will help to understand the underlying relationship between key process parameters and clogging events in continuous casting.

4.2 Modelling approaches

Various modelling approaches exist to determine the occurrence of clogging in SEN and inclusions of non-metallic particles in the steel during continuous casting. One of the modelling approaches for understanding clogging and inclusions is computational fluid dynamics (CFD) which simulates flow and

predicts blockage patterns. Multi-physics models integrate thermal, mechanical, and chemical aspects to analyse inclusion formation and accumulation. The implementation of machine learning techniques, such as neural networks, to detect patterns and predict clogging events from process data has been demonstrated [37]. Additionally, particle transport models have been used to track inclusion movements and their interactions within the SEN and stopper areas [8]. The physical and mathematical modelling of tundish operations have been the focus of several studies. Mazumdar and Guthrie provided an extensive review of studies related to tundish metallurgy and its impact in steel quality. The application of numerical and mathematical modelling to optimize the tundish operations which can lead to enhanced productivity and improved product quality [38].

4.3 Data-driven approaches

In the rapidly evolving field of materials science and manufacturing, the application of Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) techniques has garnered significant attention in the context of continuous casting processes. Such advanced computational methods can lead to significant improvements in energy efficiency, process optimization and quality control [39].

One of the primary areas where machine learning and deep learning have demonstrated their potential is in the prediction and control of material properties. These data-driven approaches have proven to be particularly effective in capturing the complex multi-dimensional relationships between the input parameters, such as chemical composition, process conditions, and the desired output properties, such as strength, toughness and ductility [40], [41], [42]. Using historical data, researchers have been able to develop predictive capabilities that can aid in the design and optimization of continuous casting processes [40].

In a recently published paper, the researchers provided comprehensive trends on the application of deep learning techniques in iron and steelmaking processes. These findings highlight modern techniques, such as deep learning, which can offer valuable insights into the dynamics of the CC process, enabling more precise control and optimization of these operations [43]. This approach is highly relevant to the task of predicting parameters and subsequent clogging events due to its ability to model complex, non-linear relationships inherent in industrial processes.

Unlike traditional modelling techniques, deep learning can automatically learn intricate patterns and dependencies from large, high-dimensional datasets, which are critical for accurately predicting dynamic process parameters over time. Moreover, deep learning models, such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks [44], excel in time-series forecasting, making them particularly suitable for predicting evolving parameters and detecting anomalous conditions, such as clogging.

In conclusion, the application of machine learning and deep learning in the field of continuous casting represents a promising area of research and development, with the potential to enhance energy efficiency, process optimization and quality control. As the field continues to evolve, the integration of these advanced computational techniques will be instrumental in addressing the challenges faced by the manufacturing industry and driving towards a more sustainable and efficient future. The above-mentioned studies have shown the potential for the use of deep learning algorithms to develop data-driven models which can assist in predicting clogging events.

4.4 Clogging detection and prediction in Continuous Casting

The application of numerical and mathematical modelling to investigate the factors leading to clogging and inclusion deposition on the nozzle wall and SEN has been extensively utilized [45]. Data-driven prediction and analysis methods, enhanced by the rise of the industrial Internet of Things (IoT)

technologies, present more distinct and effective alternatives to modelling and simulation techniques, which are more situational and simplified. These data-driven approaches excel in identifying patterns and trends within the source data, proving their effectiveness in uncovering the statistical relationships between parameters in steel fabrication and the occurrence of defects in final products. These approaches focus on the use of conventional machine-learning-based methods. In addition to their role in quality inspection within the continuous-casting process, recent research has also demonstrated the capability of machine-learning algorithms to deliver precise and interpretable predictions across a range of applications [46].

The proposed methodology is displayed in Figure 12. In the first stage, the gathered production data from the CC will be evaluated one by one. Each parameter has been selected based on the evaluation over time in relation to clogging events. After pre-processing of the data each of the parameters are selected to be fed into the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) prediction model based on deep learning algorithms. The selection of this deep learning algorithm has been grounded in a comprehensive understanding of the state-of-the-art and technical aspects.

Figure 12 - Development of the work in 2 stages.

In the second stage, the predicted parameters from stage 1 will be fed into the clogging prediction model after applying the necessary pre-processing and transformation steps. These steps will ensure that the data is properly prepared before being input into the model. In this stage a deep learning model best suited for binary classification will be selected. The model will be trained using a combination of historical real data and the predicted process parameters to detect clogging and non-clogging events in the continuous casting process.

Globally, the forecasting of this clogging event will be a major task here. To attain this objective, a deep learning model will be developed to predict the clogging event based on the parameter evolution over time. This model will also consider various steel grades and various scenarios occurring during casting of steel. The deep learning modelling will allow to understand the dependencies between clogging event and process parameters of CC. This approach is expected to extend the lifetime of refractory materials used in flow control devices and enhance overall production quality.

5 Summary and Conclusions

This report presented the available advanced digital methods used in the context of improving the energy efficiency and durability of refractories for steel ladles and continuous casting. Initially, the problems being addressed were clearly defined highlighting their relevance towards better operations. Moreover, the different predictive and prescriptive analytics techniques available to approach these issues were described, as well how they are employed to tackle similar problems from different industries.

The feasibility of using auto-encoders to reconstruct refractory temperature profiles from high-dimensional data was proven. They produced consistently lower reconstruction errors with high compression levels, although required more computation efforts than traditional methods. This result demonstrated that auto-encoders are a robust approach to encode the thermal state of the ladle. It can be used later to increase the applicability of the thermal models in real-time without compromising the approximation quality.

Another important contribution is a pioneering approach to incorporate the thermal balance into the ladle dispatching problem. It was achieved using piecewise-linear models with mixed-integer linear programming and state-of-the-art mathematical programming solvers. The development of this optimization model already enabled to determine optimal operation practices towards maximizing the energy-efficiency of steel ladles. Moreover, it provided practical insights that practitioners can use to increase the sustainability of their ladle operations.

For continuous casting, different data-driven modelling approaches were evaluated for the prediction of clogging. Preliminary results showed the feasibility of applying traditional machine learning approaches with the available historical data. However, the results highlighted the need for robust data pre-processing methods to filter outliers and improve the data quality. Hence, future work is under way in two main directions: 1) acquire more process data and 2) evaluate the use of more sophisticated techniques employing deep learning.

6 References

- [1] Worldsteel association, "World Steel in Figures - 2022." [Online]. Available: <https://worldsteel.org/steel-topics/statistics/world-steel-in-figures-2022/>
- [2] S. Biswas and D. Sarkar, "Refractories for Iron and Steel Plant," in *Introduction to Refractories for Iron- and Steelmaking*, Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020, pp. 1–97. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-43807-4_1.
- [3] M. F. Santos *et al.*, "Enhanced numerical tool to evaluate steel ladle thermal losses," *Ceram. Int.*, vol. 44, no. 11, pp. 12831–12840, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.ceramint.2018.04.092.
- [4] W. Tesselar, A. Sluiter, and M. Peekel, "Optimizing steel ladle logistics by predicting and understanding refractory wear," in *METEC-ESTAD proceedings, 2019*.
- [5] N. Walla, Z. Luo, B. Chen, Y. Krotov, and C. Zhou, "Smart Ladle: AI-Based Tool for Optimizing Caster Temperature," *Proc. AISTech*, vol. 21, 2021, doi: 10.33313/380/250.
- [6] V. Ruela, P. Van Beurden, S. Sinnema, R. Hofmann, and F. Birkelbach, "A Global Solution Approach to the Energy-Efficient Ladle Dispatching Problem With Refractory Temperature Control," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 137718–137733, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3339392.
- [7] K.-O. Yu, Ed., *Modeling for Casting and Solidification Processing*. Boca Raton: CRC Press, 2014. doi: 10.1201/9781482277333.
- [8] B. G. Thomas, "Modeling of the continuous casting of steel—past, present, and future," *Metall. Mater. Trans. B*, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 795–812, Dec. 2002, doi: 10.1007/s11663-002-0063-9.

- [9] Y. Sun and Z. Zhang, "Energy Saving and Emission Reduction from the Steel Industry: Heat Recovery from High Temperature Slags," in *Energy Solutions to Combat Global Warming*, vol. 33, X. Zhang and I. Dincer, Eds., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2017, pp. 249–280. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-26950-4_12.
- [10] A. Gerashev, "Evaluation of the potential for reduction of CO₂-emissions at the secondary metallurgy," Montanuniversität Leoben, 2016.
- [11] T. P. Fredman, J. Torrkulla, and H. Saxén, "Two-dimensional dynamic simulation of the thermal state of ladles," *Metall. Mater. Trans. B*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 323–330, Apr. 1999, doi: 10.1007/s11663-999-0061-2.
- [12] Ľ. Dorčák and J. Terpak, "Monitoring and Prediction of the Liquid Steel Temperature in the Ladle and Tundish," *Metallurgija*, vol. 45, Apr. 2006.
- [13] F. Berntsson and P. Wikström, "Thermal tracking of a ladle during production cycles," *Int. J. Comput. Methods Eng. Sci. Mech.*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 406–416, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.1080/15502287.2023.2253255.
- [14] I. Mäkelä, V.-V. Visuri, and T. Fabritius, "A mathematical model for the thermal state of a steel ladle," *Ironmak. Steelmak.*, vol. 50, no. 7, pp. 867–877, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.1080/03019233.2023.2201544.
- [15] T. P. Fredman and H. Saxén, "Model for temperature profile estimation in the refractory of a metallurgical ladle," *Metall. Mater. Trans. B*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 651–659, Jun. 1998, doi: 10.1007/s11663-998-0100-4.
- [16] H. Zhang, P. Zhou, and F. Yuan, "Effects of ladle lid or online preheating on heat preservation of ladle linings and temperature drop of molten steel," *Energy*, vol. 214, p. 118896, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2020.118896.
- [17] N. Gupta and S. Chandra, "Temperature Prediction Model for Controlling Casting Superheat Temperature," *Isij Int. - ISIJ INT*, vol. 44, pp. 1517–1526, Jan. 2004, doi: 10.2355/isijinternational.44.1517.
- [18] A. Deodhar, U. Singh, R. Shukla, B. Gautham, and A. Singh, "Fast and Accurate Prediction of Stratified Steel Temperature During Holding Period of Ladle," *Metall. Mater. Trans. B*, vol. 47B, p. 13, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s11663-016-0874-8.
- [19] S. R. M. Pirrone, C. Agabiti, A. S. Pagan, and G. Herdrich, "A Fast Thermal 1D Model to Study Aerospace Material Response Behaviors in Uncontrolled Atmospheric Entries," *Materials*, vol. 15, no. 4, p. 1505, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.3390/ma15041505.
- [20] F. He, D. He, A. Xu, H. Wang, and N. Tian, "Hybrid Model of Molten Steel Temperature Prediction Based on Ladle Heat Status and Artificial Neural Network," *J. Iron Steel Res. Int.*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 181–190, Feb. 2014, doi: 10.1016/S1006-706X(14)60028-5.
- [21] G. W. Song *et al.*, "Temperature Control Optimization in a Steel-Making Continuous Casting Process Using a Multimodal Deep Learning Approach," *Steel Res. Int.*, vol. 90, no. 12, p. 1900321, 2019, doi: 10.1002/srin.201900321.
- [22] L. Fang, F. Su, Z. Kang, and H. Zhu, "Artificial Neural Network Model for Temperature Prediction and Regulation during Molten Steel Transportation Process," *Processes*, vol. 11, no. 6, Art. no. 6, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.3390/pr11061629.
- [23] Ł. Sztangret, K. Regulski, M. Pernach, and Ł. Rauch, "Prediction of Temperature of Liquid Steel in Ladle Using Machine Learning Techniques," *Coatings*, vol. 13, no. 9, Art. no. 9, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.3390/coatings13091504.
- [24] M. Li and G. G. Wang, "A review of green shop scheduling problem," *Inf. Sci.*, vol. 589, pp. 478–496, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.ins.2021.12.122.
- [25] D. García-Menéndez, H. Morán-Palacios, F. Ortega-Fernández, and M. Díaz-Piloñeta, "Scheduling in Continuous Steelmaking Casting: A Systematic Review," *ISIJ Int.*, vol. 60, no. 6, pp. 1097–1107, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.2355/isijinternational.ISIJINT-2019-574.
- [26] M. Lee, K. Moon, K. Lee, J. Hong, and M. Pinedo, "A critical review of planning and scheduling in steel-making and continuous casting in the steel industry," *J. Oper. Res. Soc.*, pp. 1–35, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.1080/01605682.2023.2265416.

- [27] L. Tang, J. Liu, A. Rong, and Z. Yang, "A mathematical programming model for scheduling steelmaking-continuous casting production," *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, vol. 120, no. 2, pp. 423–435, Jan. 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0377-2217(99)00041-7.
- [28] H. Yuan, Y. Jing, J. Huang, and T. Ren, "Optimal research and numerical simulation for scheduling no-wait flow shop in steel production," *J. Appl. Math.*, vol. 2013, 2013, doi: 10.1155/2013/498282.
- [29] Y. Tan, T. C. E. Cheng, and M. Ji, "A multi-objective scatter search for the ladle scheduling problem," *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, vol. 52, no. 24, pp. 7513–7528, Dec. 2014, doi: 10.1080/00207543.2014.939238.
- [30] M. P. Fantì, G. Rotunno, G. Stecco, W. Ukovich, and S. Mininel, "An Integrated System for Production Scheduling in Steelmaking and Casting Plants," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 1112–1128, Apr. 2016, doi: 10.1109/TASE.2015.2477362.
- [31] Y. Tan, M. C. Zhou, Y. Zhang, X. Guo, L. Qi, and Y. Wang, "Hybrid Scatter Search Algorithm for Optimal and Energy-Efficient Steelmaking-Continuous Casting," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 1814–1828, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TASE.2020.2979079.
- [32] Z. Xu, Z. Zheng, and X. Gao, "Energy-efficient steelmaking-continuous casting scheduling problem with temperature constraints and its solution using a multi-objective hybrid genetic algorithm with local search," *Appl. Soft Comput. J.*, vol. 95, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.asoc.2020.106554.
- [33] D. Armellini, P. Borzone, S. Ceschia, L. Di Gaspero, and A. Schaerf, "Modeling and solving the steelmaking and casting scheduling problem," *Int. Trans. Oper. Res.*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 57–90, 2020, doi: 10.1111/itor.12595.
- [34] Y. jie Hong, Q. Liu, J. ping Yang, J. Wang, S. Gao, and H. hui Li, "Genetic optimization of ladle scheduling in empty-ladle operation stage based on temperature drop control," *J. Iron Steel Res. Int.*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 563–574, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s42243-021-00668-1.
- [35] V. Ruela, P. van Beurden, R. Hofmann, and F. Birkelbach, "A heuristic for fitting piecewise-linear models of bivariate functions with simplices and its application to an industrial use case," in *EURO24 proceedings*, Zenodo, Jun. 2024. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.12760505.
- [36] S. K. Michelic and C. Bernhard, "Significance of nonmetallic inclusions for the clogging phenomenon in continuous casting of steel—a review," *Steel Res. Int.*, vol. 93, no. 7, p. 2200086, 2022.
- [37] A. P. M. Diniz, P. M. Ciarelli, E. O. T. Salles, and K. F. Coco, "Use of deep neural networks for clogging detection in the Submerged Entry Nozzle of the continuous casting," *Expert Syst. Appl.*, p. 121963, 2023.
- [38] D. Mazumdar and R. L. GUTHRIE, "Mixing times and correlations for gas stirred ladle systems," *Iron Steelmak.*, vol. 26, no. 9, pp. 89–96, 1999.
- [39] R. A. Khalil, N. Saeed, M. Masood, Y. M. Fard, M.-S. Alouini, and T. Y. Al-Naffouri, "Deep learning in the industrial internet of things: Potentials, challenges, and emerging applications," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 8, no. 14, pp. 11016–11040, 2021.
- [40] A. Stoll and P. Benner, "Machine learning for material characterization with an application for predicting mechanical properties," *GAMM-Mitteilungen*, vol. 44, no. 1, p. e202100003, 2021.
- [41] M. Alvela Nieto, E. G. Nabati, D. Bode, M. A. Redecker, A. Decker, and K.-D. Thoben, "Enabling energy efficiency in manufacturing environments through deep learning approaches: lessons learned," presented at the Advances in Production Management Systems. Towards Smart Production Management Systems: IFIP WG 5.7 International Conference, APMS 2019, Austin, TX, USA, September 1–5, 2019, Proceedings, Part II, Springer, 2019, pp. 567–574.
- [42] J. C. Forsdyke, B. Zviazhynski, J. M. Lees, and G. J. Conduit, "Probabilistic selection and design of concrete using machine learning," *Data-Centric Eng.*, vol. 4, p. e9, 2023.
- [43] K. Tsutsui, T. Namba, K. Kihara, J. Hirata, S. Matsuo, and K. Ito, "Current trends on deep learning techniques applied in iron and steel making field: A review," *ISIJ Int.*, vol. 64, no. 11, pp. 1619–1640, 2024.
- [44] Y. Yu, X. Si, C. Hu, and J. Zhang, "A review of recurrent neural networks: LSTM cells and network architectures," *Neural Comput.*, vol. 31, no. 7, pp. 1235–1270, 2019.

- [45] E. Gutiérrez, S. Garcia-Hernandez, and J. De Jesús Barreto, “Mathematical Modeling of Inclusions Deposition at the Upper Tundish Nozzle and the Submerged Entry Nozzle,” *Steel Res. Int.*, vol. 87, no. 11, pp. 1406–1416, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.1002/srin.201500422.
- [46] B. G. Thomas, “Review on modeling and simulation of continuous casting,” *Steel Res. Int.*, vol. 89, no. 1, p. 1700312, 2018.